

Management of Social Relations Involving Intrigue to Authority Psyche

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Abstract

The work place as if anywhere you bring a bunch of people together, is a jumble of many different personalities. In addition to co employees who are easy to work with, will also find difficult people at work, what sets the workplace apart from many other places is that everyone even the difficult people must cooperate in order to be productive. There are different types of difficult people like; people who are talkative, people who gossip, people who complains, people who delegate, people who steal the show/credit grabber. While there is no need the magic formula to overcome the organizational politics. Hence, the study is tried to explore the required tactics, approach, sustained effort, smartness, and insightful strategies.

Keywords: Organizational politics, Strategic alliance, Intuition, and Tech-smart dynamic skills.

Introduction

Depending upon the size of the organization, there are likely to be many employees from various lifestyles, ages, and political/religious opinions. Over time, those who find familiarity with others will divide into cliques, and remain in these groups for as long as possible.

However, the diversity of the population at any one time dictates that there will inevitably be those within the business, regardless of their faction or clique, who holds (or is seen as holding) a large amount of power within the office. Employees such as this may blame others for their mistakes, or attempt to belittle or undermine colleagues and co-workers, alienating them and leading to a situation of organization politics, the struggle of power or authority within an organization.

1. Principles for organizational politics

1.1. Manage: Using the good manners will help you make a good impression with your boss and your co-workers. Managing office etiquettes include everything from the proper way to use email to knowing when, where and how to use your cell phone while at work. Do not wait until

you're fired, laid off, burned out, or fed up to revitalize your career. Reinvent your career on an ongoing basis.

1.2. Converse: Everyone you talk to judges or evaluate your worth. Make that conversation worth something by focusing on the other person and not yourself. In addition, you never know where the next great opportunity can come from.

1.3. Strength focus: Do what you are best at and for what you have a passion. Do not focus on your weaknesses; Focus on your strengths and not on weakness.

1.4. Workaholics: Do not be a workaholic, typically, these people burn out and never regain their previous success levels, and often pay a personal price for their behavior.

1.5. Relationship: Employees should strive to maintain good relationships with colleagues, endeavoring to earn respect and trust through hard work and co-operation. Businesses look favorably on employees who support and praise those around them, and are more likely to offer a promotion to him or her than another is, of course the bottom line is important, but not at the expense of people. Speak to people around you, develop relations, speak with assertiveness, and show empathy in your behaviors.

1.6. Listen than speak: Develop the discipline to listen 80 percent of the time and talk 20 percent.

1.7. Team network: Employees within a business often divide into smaller factions where similarity of views or interest is found. An employee who is adept in managing office politics should endeavor to network and establish relationships across all groups.

Whilst it is recommended that employees establish contacts and relationships within the work place, it is strongly advised that gossip be avoided at all times. It would be considered unethical to spread rumor that could damage a colleague's reputation, and if discovered to be the source of the rumor, the employee could face disciplinary action.

By regularly networking with colleagues, the employee can discover and understand the power structures behind the business, such as colleagues or managers who wield a greater influence than their equals do. This knowledge can then be used to the employee's advantage.

1.8. Challenge hostile: An employee may find a particular co-worker especially difficult to establish a relationship with, and could even experience the colleague actively setting out to undermine authority and provoke frustration. If this occurs, the employee should approach the colleague privately, calmly and rationally explain any issues, and request that the colleague refrain from continuing with the provocative behavior. Only if this does not have an effect should the employee seek assistance from those with greater authority within the hierarchy.

1.9. Be friend those with greater power: Whilst avoiding "brown-nosing", it is greatly beneficial for the employee to strike a rapport with those of higher authority or influence within the business. This would make it easier for the employee to voice opinions, and may provide a means through which greater authority can be obtained within his or her own role.

Ultimately, each employee must focus on his or her own individual career objectives, and strive to impress those higher in the chain of authority through hard work, dedication, and diligence. This will undoubtedly be noticed after time and possibly open further opportunities for career progression.

A combination of all the points listed above will ultimately stand the employee in good stead to effectively manage organizational politicks indulge in them whilst still furthering his or her career.

Peak performance comes from individuals and teams who know how to leverage their differences as well as their similarities. In today's complex operating environment, where human capital account for much of a company's intangible valuation, the ability to lead and leverage critical relationships becomes a strong differentiator. colleagues' high-level corporate experience adds to the breadth and depth of knowledge of management styles across all levels. It is the employees who help companies elevate key relationships that drive business development, inclusive leadership, and client retention, developing relationships that work.

Over the years, the specific of our work have been broad; women's initiatives; organization redesign; post-merger and culture change initiatives; team-based solutions and employee development. The commonality is a sharp focus on what it takes to inspire the right people to work together on organizational goals because they understand what is needed; because they understand what is in it for them and because they understand how to make it work.

2. Tech-smart dynamic skills

2.1. Never try to harm colleagues or to get into trouble: as there is a saying "What come around go around".

2.2. Keep personal feelings separate from professional relationships: No matter how much you don't like the co-workers or bosses. A good employee knows when to behave professionally during work. If you are able to smile, behave and work professionally when working together with the co-workers or bosses that you don't like. You are a real winner. But if you have decided to show your unhappiness or frustrations to them, you are just falling into their traps as they can use these as excuses to degrade your work performances.

2.1. Strategic alliance: try to find and form an alliance in the office. Find out whom you can trust and have common or similar objectives in the organization. Get together and form a strategic alliance. It will benefit all in the long run.

2.2. Paycheck contrast: do not compare salary or bonus with co-workers or allow others to compare and comment. It will only lower the morale in the office. If you feel that you deserve more, talk to your direct boss or superior based on your work performance and merits.

2.3. Healthy relationships with boss and subordinates: Remember one cannot be running the whole show in the company, need the supports from various parties in the organization to achieve the best performance.

3. Conclusion

The philosopher Plato said, "One of the penalties for refusing to participate in politics is that you end up being governed by your inferiors." And this hold true today in the workplace; If don't participate in the political game, risk not having a say in what happens and allowing people with less experience, skill or knowledge to influence the decisions being made around you. Office Politics are a fact of life. Wise politicking will help, get what in the world of work without compromising others in the process. Learn to use its power positively while diffusing the efforts of those who abuse it. Creating a motivating organization can pose an incredible challenge for every leader or manager. We know that motivation leads to greater work performance in organizations. We also know that managing or motivating people is an art. It comes with creativity, intuition, experience, stewardship, and steadfast faith in the goodness of people.

The people that drive the organization to succeed or fail. As long as do not lose sight of this straight, unvarnished truth, will be on the right path to building a truly people-based organization one that requires managers to master the art of people management in order to be successful in the 21st century. There is no other route or detour to creating a high-performance organization. Organizational transformation from effectiveness to greatness starts with the recognition that the people are indeed most important asset and deserve to be managed every day as such. Finally, when we stand by our core values, being sincere and holding high integrity, soft power attracts and people are persuaded and certainly trust.

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